

Mercury seen from Mars (local Extrema of apparent brightness from 2008-2014)

Harald Schröer

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An observer stays in a space ship that circles round the Mars.

Explanations: mag = stellar magnitude, °=degree, ' = angular minute, " = angular second

AE= astronomical unit=149598500 km

Date	apparent Brightness [mag]	Phase in per cent	Distance of Mercury from Mars [AE]	Angle-distance to Sun [°]	apparent Dia-meter["]	Distance of Mercury to Sun [AE]
10.1.-13.1.2008	-0.10	71-82 decreasing	1.72-1.81 decreasing	10.61-11.62 increasing	3.7-3.9 increasing	0.35-0.38 decreasing
2.2.2008	weaker than +6.50	<1	1.30	1.11-1.12 increasing	5.1	0.31-0.32 increasing
13.4.-16.4.2008	-0.34	80-88 decreasing	1.84-1.91 decreasing	7.69-8.97 increasing	3.6-3.7 increasing	0.33-0.35 decreasing
8.5.2008	weaker than +7.00	<1	1.31-1.32 decreasing	1.33-1.34 increasing	5.1	0.35-0.36 increasing
14.7.-17.7.2008	-0.59	89-95 decreasing	1.88-1.93 decreasing	4.99-6.67 increasing	3.5-3.6 increasing	0.31-0.33 decreasing
14.8.2008	weaker than +8.50	<1	1.21-1.22 decreasing	0.88-0.89 increasing	5.4-5.6 increasing	0.41
14.10.-17.10.2008	-0.83	96-100 decreasing	1.83-1.87 decreasing	1.42-4.08 increasing	3.6-3.7 increasing	0.30-0.32 decreasing
27.11.2008	weaker than +9.50	<1	1.04	0.86	6.4	0.46-0.47 increasing
14.1.-16.1.2009	-0.99	98-100 increasing	1.74-1.75 increasing	0.87-2.90 decreasing	3.8-3.9 decreasing	0.30-0.31 increasing
17.3.2009	weaker than +6.50	<1	0.97-0.98 increasing	2.20-2.22 decreasing	6.8-6.9 decreasing	0.41-0.42 decreasing
15.4.-18.4.2009	-0.91	88-94 increasing	1.60-1.65 increasing	6.73-8.43 decreasing	4.1-4.2 decreasing	0.31-0.32 increasing
28.6.2009	weaker than +7.00	<1	1.08	0.77-0.78 decreasing	6.2	0.34
19.7.-20.7.2009	-0.50	76-80 increasing	1.58-1.61 increasing	11.24-11.68 decreasing	4.2-4.3 decreasing	0.33-0.35 increasing
23.8.-28.8.2009	+0.16	92-96 decreasing	1.85-1.90 decreasing	7.28-9.57 increasing	3.5-3.6	0.46-0.47 decreasing
10.9.-11.9.2009	+0.08	71-74 decreasing	1.63-1.65 decreasing	14.11-14.24 increasing	4.1	0.41-0.42 decreasing
3.10.-4.10.2009	weaker than +6.50	<1	1.22	0.56	5.5	0.31
23.10.-27.10.2009	+0.10	65-77 increasing	1.63-1.74 increasing	12.82-13.62 decreasing	3.8-4.1 decreasing	0.38-0.41 increasing
13.11.-19.11.2009	+0.26	96-99 increasing	1.99-2.04 increasing	3.35-6.36 decreasing	3.3-3.4 decreasing	0.46-0.47 increasing
16.12.-18.12.2009	-0.15	75-82 decreasing	1.76-1.82 decreasing	10.24-10.90 increasing	3.7-3.8 increasing	0.35-0.37 decreasing
7.1.2010	weaker than +7.00	<1	1.31	1.19-1.20 increasing	5.1	0.32-0.33 increasing
19.3.-21.3.2010	-0.39	83-89 decreasing	1.86-1.91 decreasing	7.42-8.35 increasing	3.5-3.6 increasing	0.32-0.34 decreasing
13.4.2010	weaker than +7.50	<1	1.30	1.31-1.32 increasing	5.1	0.36-0.37 increasing
19.6.-21.6.2010	-0.64	91-96 decreasing	1.88-1.92 decreasing	4.58-6.07 increasing	3.5-3.6 increasing	0.31-0.32 decreasing
22.7.2010	weaker than +9.50	<1	1.17-1.18 decreasing	0.67-0.68 increasing	5.7	0.42-0.43 increasing
19.9.-20.9.2010	-0.88	99-100 decreasing	1.83-1.84 decreasing	1.88-2.22 increasing	3.6-3.7 increasing	0.31
5.11.2010	weaker	<1	1.01	1.30-1.31	6.6	0.46-0.47

19.12.-21.12.2010	than +8.50 -1.00	97-100 increasing	1.71-1.73 increasing	decreasing 2.06-3.69 decreasing	3.9	decreasing 0.30-0.31 increasing
22.2.-23.2.2011	weaker than +6.50	<1	0.98-0.99 increasing	2.06-2.08 decreasing	6.8	0.39-0.40 decreasing
21.3.-23.3.2011	-0.86	86-90 increasing	1.59-1.63 increasing	8.13-9.00 decreasing	4.1-4.2 decreasing	0.31-0.33 increasing
4.6.2011	weaker than +8.00	<1	1.11	0.46-0.47 decreasing	6.0	0.32-0.33 decreasing
24.6.-26.6.2011	-0.39	73-79 increasing	1.58-1.63 increasing	11.60-12.19 decreasing	4.1-4.3 decreasing	0.34-0.36 increasing
27.7.-31.7.2011	+0.17	96-98 decreasing	1.91-1.94 decreasing	5.03-6.68 increasing	3.4-3.5 increasing	0.46-0.47 decreasing
16.8.-19.8.2011	+0.04	69-77 decreasing	1.63-1.71 decreasing	13.06-13.66 increasing	3.9-4.1 increasing	0.39-0.41 decreasing
9.9.2011	weaker than +7.00	<1	1.25	0.72-0.74 decreasing	5.3	0.31
30.9.-3.10.2011	+0.20	67-76 increasing	1.67-1.75 increasing	13.25-13.80 decreasing	3.8-4.0 decreasing	0.40-0.42 increasing
18.10.-21.10.2011	+0.30	94-96 increasing	1.99-2.02 increasing	6.55-7.69 decreasing	3.3-3.4 decreasing	0.46-0.47 increasing
20.11.-23.11.2011	-0.19	75-84 decreasing	1.77-1.86 decreasing	9.40-10.53 increasing	3.6-3.8 increasing	0.34-0.37 decreasing
13.12.2011	weaker than +7.00	<1	1.31-1.32 decreasing	1.25-1.27 increasing	5.1	0.32-0.33 increasing
22.2.-23.2.2012	-0.44	87-89 decreasing	1.89-1.91 decreasing	7.28-7.58 increasing	3.5-3.6 increasing	0.32-0.33 decreasing
19.3.2012	weaker than +7.50	<1	1.28-1.29 decreasing	1.26-1.27 increasing	5.2	0.37-0.38 increasing
24.5.-25.5.2012	-0.69	93-97 decreasing	1.88-1.91 decreasing	4.23-5.36 increasing	3.5-3.6 increasing	0.31-0.32 decreasing
27.6.2012	weaker than +9.50	<1	1.15	0.40-0.41 increasing	5.8	0.43-0.44 increasing
23.8.-25.8.2012	-0.91	98-100 decreasing	1.81-1.83 decreasing	0.26-2.47 increasing	3.7	0.30-0.31 increasing
13.10.2012	weaker than +8.00	<1	0.99	1.71-1.72 decreasing	6.8	0.46-0.47 decreasing
23.11.-24.11.2012	-1.00	96-98 increasing	1.69-1.71 increasing	3.53-4.48 decreasing	3.9-4.0 decreasing	0.30-0.32 increasing
30.1.2013	weaker than +6.50	<1	1.00-1.01 increasing	1.81-1.83 decreasing	6.6-6.7 decreasing	0.38-0.39 decreasing
23.2.-25.2.2013	-0.79	82-89 increasing	1.57-1.63 increasing	8.71-10.08 decreasing	4.1-4.3 decreasing	0.31-0.33 increasing
10.5.2013	weaker than +8.00	<1	1.14	0.18	5.9	0.32
28.5.-1.6.2013	-0.27	68-79 increasing	1.57-1.67 increasing	11.75-12.70 decreasing	4.0-4.3 decreasing	0.35-0.37 increasing
28.6.-4.7.2013	+0.18	98-100 decreasing	1.96-1.98 decreasing	1.84-4.82 increasing	3.4	0.46-0.47 decreasing
21.7.-25.7.2013	+0.00	69-80 decreasing	1.65-1.75 decreasing	12.15-13.02 increasing	3.8-4.1 increasing	0.37-0.40 decreasing
14.8.2013	weaker than +7.00	<1	1.27	0.87-0.98 decreasing	5.3	0.31
5.9.-10.9.2013	+0.30	67-79 increasing	1.69-1.82 increasing	13.03-14.07 decreasing	3.7-4.0 decreasing	0.41-0.44 increasing
19.9.-22.9.2013	+0.34	89-93 increasing	1.95-2.00 increasing	8.82-9.94 decreasing	3.3-3.4 decreasing	0.46-0.47 increasing
25.10.-27.10.2013	-0.24	78-84 decreasing	1.81-1.87 decreasing	9.09-9.88 increasing	3.6-3.7 increasing	0.34-0.36 decreasing
17.11.2013	weaker than +6.50	<1	1.32-1.33 decreasing	1.30-1.31 increasing	5.0	0.33-0.34 increasing
26.1.-28.1.2014	-0.48	85-93 decreasing	1.87-1.94 decreasing	6.06-7.75 increasing	3.4-3.6 increasing	0.31-0.33 decreasing
22.2.2014	weaker than +7.50	<1	1.26-1.27 decreasing	1.19-1.20 increasing	5.3	0.39
27.4.-30.4.2014	-0.73	93-99 decreasing	1.86-1.91 decreasing	2.98-5.40 increasing	3.5-3.6 increasing	0.30-0.32 decreasing
4.6.2014	weaker	<1	1.11	0.07	6.0	0.44-0.45

28.7.-31.7.2014	than +10.00 -0.94	99-100 decreasing	1.79-1.80 decreasing	0.99-1.84 increasing	3.7-3.8 increasing	increasing 0.31
21.9.2014	weaker than +7.00	<1	0.97-0.98 increasing	2.02-2.03 decreasing	6.8-6.9 decreasing	0.45-0.46 decreasing
28.10.-30.10.2014	-0.98	93-98 increasing	1.65-1.70 increasing	3.86-6.39 decreasing	3.9-4.1 decreasing	0.30-0.32 increasing
31.12.2014	+3.15 decreasing	6	1.02	7.81	6.6	0.40

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